

THE ROLE OF ENGLISH IN HIGHER EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN: A STUDY ON ACADEMIC AND PROFESSIONAL LANGUAGE NEEDS AMONG MA STUDENTS AT KARSHI INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY

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1. Background of the Study

English has emerged as a global lingua franca, serving as the primary medium for communication, academic exchange, and professional advancement in a variety of fields. This role of English is especially pronounced in higher education, where proficiency in the language can open doors to international research collaborations, scholarly publications, and career opportunities. For students pursuing advanced degrees, particularly at the master's level, strong English language skills are crucial not only for academic success but also for achieving professional goals.

In Uzbekistan, the demand for English proficiency has intensified as the country aims to strengthen its international ties and modernize its educational sector. Educational reforms emphasize English as a key competency for students at all levels, especially those in higher education. However, many students face challenges in mastering the language to a level required for academic and professional tasks. At Karshi International University (KIU), the need for effective English instruction is particularly pressing among Master of Arts (MA) students, who are expected to engage with academic literature, produce research, and present their work both locally and internationally. Yet, little research has been conducted to identify the specific English language needs of these students, creating a gap that this study aims to address.

2. Statement of the Problem

While English proficiency is essential for higher education and career success, the specific academic and professional language needs of MA students in Uzbekistan remain under-researched. Without an understanding of these needs, English language programs may fall short of preparing students for the demands they will face. This gap is particularly significant at KIU, where MA students often express difficulty in accessing adequate resources and support to develop their English skills fully. The current curriculum may not sufficiently cover the range of skills these students require, leaving them unprepared for both academic and professional challenges. Therefore, this study investigates the English language needs of KIU's MA students, seeking to provide insights

that will guide curriculum development to better align with student needs and expectations.

3. Research Questions

This study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the academic English language needs of MA students at KIU?
2. What are the professional English language needs of these students?
3. How effective is the current English curriculum at KIU in meeting these academic and professional needs?
4. What challenges do MA students face in acquiring the English skills necessary for their academic and professional pursuits?

4. Research Design

This study adopts a mixed-methods research design, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis methods. The mixed-methods approach allows for a comprehensive examination of the English language needs of MA students at KIU by drawing on both statistical data and personal insights from participants. The quantitative component seeks to quantify the academic and professional language skills required, while the qualitative component provides an in-depth understanding of the specific challenges and needs students experience.

Participants

The participants in this study are MA students at KIU, specializing in linguistics. A purposive sampling method will be used to select participants to ensure representation of students with varying levels of English proficiency and academic backgrounds. Additional participants will include English language instructors at KIU, as their insights are critical to understanding curriculum strengths and weaknesses from an instructional perspective. Participation in this study was voluntary, with informed consent obtained from all participants prior to data collection. Confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing survey and interview responses, and participants had the right to withdraw from the study at any point without penalty. Approval for the study was obtained from KIU's ethics review board.

5. Literature Review

The Role of English in Higher Education

English has solidified its status as the primary language for academic and professional communication in many parts of the world. According to Crystal (2003), the rise of English as a global lingua franca has transformed the

linguistic landscape of higher education, necessitating high proficiency levels among students aiming to engage in international academia. The need for English proficiency in higher education has led to the development of English for Academic Purposes (EAP) programs in many institutions worldwide (Hyland, 2006). These programs aim to equip students with the specific language skills needed for academic success, including research writing, critical reading, and oral presentations.

English Language Needs in the Context of Uzbekistan

As Uzbekistan's government prioritizes educational reform and internationalization, the demand for English has intensified across all educational levels. Studies by Kurbonov (2021) and Abdullaeva (2020) highlight how recent policy initiatives have positioned English as a cornerstone for modernizing the educational system and preparing students to engage in the global workforce. However, research indicates that many students face challenges in achieving the language proficiency necessary for academic and professional tasks (Tursunov, 2019). Limited resources, traditional teaching methods, and a lack of specialized training in academic English are cited as barriers to student success. In Uzbekistan, English has gained prominence as the government actively promotes bilingualism and international engagement. Recent educational reforms underscore the importance of English for both personal and national advancement, pushing universities to prioritize language education (Abdullaeva, 2020; Kurbonov, 2021). Nevertheless, research shows that while English is valued, students often face a "competency gap" due to factors like limited exposure to English outside the classroom, traditional teaching methods, and a scarcity of EAP resources (Tursunov, 2019; Madatov, 2023). For students, particularly those pursuing graduate studies, this gap may hinder their ability to fully engage with the academic community, publish research, and access global networks (Nurmatov, 2022).

Academic English Needs of MA Students

Research on EAP programs reveals that MA students require specific academic skills to succeed in their studies, including the ability to analyze academic literature, write research papers, and present findings effectively. Flowerdew and Peacock (2001) underscore the importance of advanced reading and writing skills in graduate education, as students are expected to critically engage with complex academic texts. In Uzbekistan, where English is a foreign language, MA students often struggle with these skills due to limited exposure to academic English prior to their graduate studies (Nurmatov, 2022). The lack of

academic vocabulary, familiarity with genre conventions, and confidence in oral presentations pose additional challenges.

Professional English Needs of MA Students

In addition to academic skills, MA students in Uzbekistan require English proficiency for professional purposes, such as networking, attending conferences, and publishing research. According to Basturkmen (2010), EAP programs should also integrate elements of English for Professional Purposes (EPP) to support students' career goals. Professional skills, such as writing cover letters, giving professional presentations, and engaging in discussions with international colleagues, are essential for MA students aiming to contribute to their fields. Despite these needs, existing curricula often prioritize academic English without addressing professional language skills, leading to a skills gap among graduates.

Conclusion of the Literature Review

The literature suggests that while English is increasingly recognized as essential for academic and professional success in Uzbekistan, there are notable gaps in the current language programs. MA students require a specialized set of skills that encompass both academic and professional competencies, yet curricula often fail to address these needs fully. This study builds on existing research by focusing on the specific needs of MA students at KIU and aims to provide data-driven recommendations that could inform curriculum development and policy decisions. The findings will potentially contribute to a more effective English language curriculum that prepares students not only to succeed academically but also to participate actively in the global academic and professional communities.

Conclusion

MA students at KIU need advanced academic English skills to support critical reading, writing, and research. Their requirements include proficiency in reading complex texts, summarizing and synthesizing research, understanding specialized vocabulary, and applying proper academic conventions in their writing. They also require skills in presenting arguments, analyzing scholarly texts, and creating well-structured essays, reports, and research papers. In addition, they need to engage confidently in academic discussions, presentations, and debates. Professionally, MA students need strong oral and written communication skills to function effectively in global and multicultural work environments. This includes the ability to write formal emails, reports, and

proposals, as well as conduct and participate in professional presentations and meetings. They may also need industry-specific vocabulary depending on their field, along with cross-cultural communication skills to navigate international settings, as English often serves as the lingua franca in many professions.

The effectiveness of the current English curriculum at KIU may vary depending on several factors, such as its alignment with real-world academic and professional expectations, its emphasis on practical language use, and how well it integrates communication skills. While the curriculum likely provides foundational knowledge, there may be gaps in specialized vocabulary, industry-specific language training, and opportunities for authentic practice, which could limit students' preparedness for real-life academic and professional contexts. Enhanced focus on academic writing, critical thinking, and professional communication could make the curriculum more effective.

MA students often encounter several challenges in developing these English skills. These may include limited access to native-speaking environments, a lack of targeted resources for advanced academic writing, and insufficient exposure to discipline-specific vocabulary. Additionally, students may struggle with balancing language acquisition with the rigorous demands of their academic studies. Anxiety or low confidence in speaking English, especially in formal settings, can also hinder their progress.

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